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THE EFFECTIVENESS OF DIGITAL ADVERTISING ON MODERN CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOR WITH REFERENCE TO AIRTEL

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Abstract

The purpose of advertising is to influence viewers, readers, or listeners to take some kind of action. In order to convince prospective consumers to buy or use that specific brand, it contains the name of the product or service and how it may benefit the consumer. As mass manufacturing increased in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, modern advertising evolved.

Through branding, which is the practice of repeating a product name or image in an attempt to have customers identify the brand with relevant attributes, commercial marketers often aim to boost the consumption of their goods or services. These messages may be sent using a variety of media, including new media like websites and text messaging, as well as more conventional media like newspapers, magazines, radio, television, and direct mail. An advertising agency may post advertisements on behalf of a business or other entity.

Political parties, interest groups, religious institutions, and governmental organisations are examples of non-commercial advertising that invest funds to promote goods and services other than consumer goods. Public service announcements and other free forms of persuasion may be used by nonprofit organisations.

I. INTRODUCTION

Consumer behavior refers to the mental and emotional process and the observable behavior of consumers during searching, purchasing and post consumption of a product or service.

Consumer behavior involves study of how people buy, what they buy, when they buy and why they buy. It blends the elements from psychology, sociology, sociopsychology, anthropology and economics. It also tries to assess the influence on the consumer from groups such as family, friends, reference groups and society in general.

Buyer behavior has two aspects: the final purchase activity visible to any observer and the detailed or short decision process that may

involve the interplay of a number of complex variables not visible to anyone.

Advertising has become as much a part of our lives as breathing. When you turn on the TV, open your mailbox, drive down the street, pick up your phone, or surf the Internet you come face to face with some facet of advertising. In his essay "How Advertising Informs To Our Benefit," John E. Calfee explores the concept that "advertising provides society with useful information that we might not otherwise receive". I would have to agree that advertising has a profound effect on our society as a whole. It has developed into one of our cultures primary sources for information, solutions, ideas, and entertainment.

In view of the fact that advertisers reach a broad spectrum of people, by using resources such as television, magazines, newspapers, billboards, the Internet, etc. it is easy to see how they can have such an impact on society. For Instance, "In 1984, to increase consumer awareness and consumption, Kellogg's started using health claims as part of their advertising campaigns". Other markets soon followed suit with products ranging from bread to toothpaste. Rapidly advertising became a medium for providing essential health information to consumers, who for one reason or another, may never have received this information, proving Calfree's theory, "advertising is necessary for consumer welfare".

But what about advertising for products such as, cigarettes, alcohol, and violent video games. The fact is that the advertising of such products brings about consumer awareness which can prove to be very beneficial in itself. Take violent computer games for instance. A great deal of controversy over the harmful effects these games can have on our society is a direct result of advertising. Controversial advertising brings about media coverage, which leads to even greater consumer awareness. This exposure gives parents vital information, which can help them in protecting their children against such harmful products. Regardless of whether advertising is negative or positive the information and awareness it creates is beneficial to consumer welfare to some extent.

There in lies the love-hate relationship consumer's have with advertising. We live in a busy, fast-paced society. Therefore, advertisers must catch our attention quickly, must appeal to our emotions, communicate a products benefit in a few quick words, and create a lasting impression if they want to be affective.

"As we spread wings to expand our capabilities and explore new horizons, the fundamental focus remains unchanged: seek out the best technology in the world

and put it at the service of our ultimate user: our customer."

Promotion is true that products are manufactured to satisfy the needs of the consumers.. But alone is not enough. Today the responsibility of the manufacturers does not cease with physical production whatever may be the nature of the product. The present day marketers are consumer oriented where it is the duty of the manufacturers to know from where, when, how and what price the products would be available. Successful marketing consists in offering the right product of the right price of the right place (and time) with right promotion.

Generally marketing communication is undertaken to pass on the message of a product or sale to the ultimate consumers. Thus, there are three elements in this process.

The purpose of advertising is motivating but to sell something a product, a service or an AIRTEL. The real objective of advertising is effective communication between producers and consumers. In other words the ultimate purpose all advertising is "Increased awareness" list of the following specific objectives of advertising.

The process of selling is ensured by personal selling supposed by advertising and sales promotion. Of these three methods personal selling occupies the predominant role mainly because of the personal element involves. It may be described as a personal source rendered to the community in connection with marketing of goods. It is a marketing process with which consumers are personally persuaded to by goods and services offered by a manufacturer. The most powerful element in the promotional mix is salesman ship, is not something very new. Even centuraries ago salesman ship was practiced in Greece and Rome. According to Peter Drucker Cyrus Mecornie was the first man to use modern technique of selling.

Features:

1. It helps to establish a cordial and obiding relationship between the organization and its customers.
2. It is a creative art. It creates wants a new.
3. It is a science, in the sense that “One human mind influences another human mind”.
4. Personal selling imparts knowledge and technical assistance to the consumers.

Promotion includes all those functions, which have to do with the marketing of a product all other activities designed to increase and expand the market. But it is clearly distinguished from advertising and personal selling, through basic aim or all the three is one and the same viz., to increase the volume of sales.

“Sales promotion in a specific sense, refers to those sales activities that supplement both personal selling and advertising and co-ordinationate them and help t make them effective, such as displays, shows and expositions, demonstrations and other non recurrent selling efforts not in the ordinary routine”.

In a general sense the sales promotion includes “ personal selling, advertising and supplementary selling activities”.

Evaluation of Sales Promotion:

Two decades ago, there was no agreement among the marketing people that there was a separate sales promotion function. In those days, promotion was a “share- run to gain a short run good”. The importance of sales promotion is modern marketing has increased mainly an account of its ability in promoting sales and preparing the ground for future expansion. The main objective of sales promotion is to attract the prospective buyer towards the product.

PUBLICITY

The publicity is derived as “Any form of commercially significant news about a product, and institution, a service, or a person published I a space or radio i.e. not paid for by the sponsor”. In short advertisement is paid form of publicity. It is to be noted here that though the terms ‘ADVERTISING ‘AND ‘Publicity’ or differences in the field of marketing, both are used interchangeably.

The media are broadly classified into direct indirect. Direct method of advertising refers to such methods used by the advertiser with which he could establish a direct contact with the prospects. Most of the media are indirect in nature EX: Free Publicity, cinema, etc.

II. OBJECTIVES

- ✓ To know the customer opinion about tariff rates of Airtel.
- ✓ To know the brand loyalty of Airtel.
- ✓ To know the influencing factors of Airtel.
- ✓ To know the market share of the Airtel.
- ✓ To know the sources of awareness for the customers.
- ✓ To know the customer satisfaction on network of Airtel.
- ✓ To know the satisfaction on Services Provided by Airtel.
- ✓ To know the satisfaction of customers on Recharge and Top up cards when compare to other competitors.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

One of the important tools for conducting marketing researching is the availability of necessary and useful data. Data collection is more of an than science the methods of marketing research are in a way the methods of data collection. The sources of information fall under two categories.

Internal sources:

Every company has to keep certain records such as accounts, records, reports, etc., these records provide sample

information which can organizations usually keeps collecting in its working.

External sources:

When internal records are insufficient and required information is not available, the organizations will have to depend on external sources. The external sources of data are:

Primary data:

Primary data are data gathered for a specific purpose or for a specific research report.

For systematically collecting the data the closed end questionnaire is used. The questionnaire consists of questions relating to various aspects of the study for proper data collection the questionnaire is divided into 2 sections. Both the sections are meant for the respondent only.

Secondary data:

Secondary data are data that are collected for another purpose and already exist somewhere. Data pertaining to company is collected from company web site company catalogues and magazines. The company profile gives a detailed report of history various products manufacture by its etc.

**IV. METHOD OF RESEARCH
SURVEY METHOD:**

A survey is a complete operation, which requires some technical knowledge survey methods are mostly personal in character. Surveys are best suited forgetting primary data. The researcher obtains information from the respondents by interviewing them.

SAMPLING:

It is not always necessary to collect data from whole universe. A small representative sample may serve the purpose. A sample means a small group should be emanative cross section and

really “representative” in character. This selection process is called sampling.

SAMPLE SIZE:

Samples are devices for learning about large masses by observing a few individuals. The selected sample is 100.

Sampling plan:

1. SAMPLING UNIT -The business people, professionals are survived
2. SAMPLING PROCEDURE - Stratified random sampling method is chosen.

The data collected from both the primary and secondary sources is tabulated and presented in a systematic form prior to classification and interpretation.

METHOD OF SAMPLING**RANDOM SAMPLING METHOD**

The method adopted here is random sampling method. A random sample is one where each item in the universe has as equal chance of known opportunity of being selected.

RESEARCH INSTRUMENT**QUESTIONNAIRE:**

A Questionnaire is carefully completed logical sequence of question directed to a define objective. It is the out line of what information is required and the framework on which the data is built upon. Questionnaire is son commonly used in securing market information that its preparation deserves utmost skill and care.

LIMITATIONS

1. Time is the main limitation for the study, as project was restricted only for 45 days.
2. The methods used in this project are random sampling methods and results obtained may not be accurately fully accurate and believable.

3. The research has been centered to only a hundred Customers of Airtel, rather than innumerable Customers dealing with different products of different brands across the globe.
4. The analysis is purely based on closed ended questions and due their deliberate manipulation, important information may be lost and even barriers of communication would cause a limitation.
5. The whole project research was confined to only customers of Airtel
6. The research was done with the help of employees of the organization for some of the dealers and their barriers of communication or way to represent the topic would differ and actual information would be lost.
7. The dealers responded during the survey were possessing primary education and their views would not be able to provide the required information

CUSTOMER GETTING SMARTER

A competitor, in order to achieve the loyalty of the customers, offer an endless information flow on the products and services and thereby continuously educates the customer about the opportunities in the market. Therefore today even an ordinary person, is in possession of the large amount of data to use for the purpose of making a decision as to which products/ services he would go in for. The competitive environment is making the customer wisher day by day and he is able to take a large number of decisions on his own. The experts' advice of the olden days is being replaced by the customer's own wisdom. This is making the market place more complicated and unpredictable. The customer is getting smarter today and he is able to decide his own money's worth and

therefore, organization across the board are 'pursuing the customer's views to streamline their business strategies to remain customer-worthy.

People are the prime factor for any organization to maintain the effectiveness and thus develop the right focus for the people, so that each one perceives as clearly as possible his position in the cycle of growth and prosperity of the organization. Agendas will have to be drawn in such a manner and communicated so effectively that the individual is able to enjoy a meaningful life in the organization, endowed with authority and responsibility for the role he plays.

“One should be able to see for oneself the impact of the contributions one has made towards the growth and prosperity cycle of the organization. As a matter of fact the relationship between the people and the organization should be so designed that each one is here to experience the pleasure of winning and pain of losing. People alone are of no significance unless and until they have an intimate and continuous interaction with the process”.

Therefore organization have to take continuous care to update their quality of the people and that of processes simultaneously so that a healthy relationship is built up and maintained making the relationship happy and healthy one. This, when done, should generate in people a sense of entrepreneurship ownership of the organization.

It can be defined as the process by which an individual selects, organizes, and interprets stimuli into a meaningful and coherent picture of the world. A stimulus is a unit of input to any of the senses. Examples of stimulus ie, sensory input include products, packages, brand names, advertisements, and commercials, sensory receptor.

Marketers do not want their target audience to look only at the models in their ads. They want to communicate something about their products as well. Marketers often use attractive models, humour, other factors to attract the target market's interest. Information processing is a series of activities by which stimuli are perceived, transformed in to information, and stored.

Consumer Buying Behavior

Possibly the most challenging concept in marketing deals with understanding why buyers do what they do (or don't do). But such knowledge is critical for marketers since Wanting a strong understanding of buyer behavior will help shed light on what is important to the customer and also suggest the important influences on customer decision-making. Using this information, marketers can create marketing programs that they believe will be of interest to customers.

As you might guess, factors affecting how customers make decisions are extremely complex. Buyer behavior is deeply rooted in psychology with dashes of sociology thrown in just to make things more interesting. Since every person in the world is different, it is impossible to have simple rules that explain how buying decisions are made. But those who have spent many years analyzing customer activity have presented us with useful "guidelines" in how someone decides whether or not to make a purchase.

In fact, pick up any textbook that examines customer behavior and each seems to approach

it from a different angle. The perspective we take is to touch on just the basic concepts that appear to be commonly accepted as influencing customer behavior. We will devote two sections of the Principles of Marketing Tutorials to customer behavior. In this section we will examine the buying behavior of consumers (i.e., when people buy for personal reasons) while in the Business Buying Behavior tutorial we will examine factors that influence buyer's decisions in the business market.

V. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

AGE GROUP OF THE RESPONDENTS:

The below table shows the age group of the respondents surveyed:

AGE	No Of Respondents
18-28	8
28-38	28
38-48	10
Above 48	54
Total	100

INFERENCE: From the above table, 8% of the respondents belong to the age group of 18-28 years, 28% of the respondents belong to the age group of 28-38 years, 10% of the respondents belong to the age group of 38-48 years, 54% of the respondents belong to the age group of above 48 years.

AGE GROUP OF THE RESPONDENTS:

The below table shows the age group of the respondents surveyed:

THE ANALYSIS TYPES OF CONSUMERS OF PURCHASE OF AIRTEL

AGE	No Of Respondents
18-28	8
28-38	28
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INFERENCE: From the above table, 8% of the respondents belong to the age group of 18-28 years, 28% of the respondents belong to the age group of 28-38 years, 10% of the respondents belong to the age group of 38-48 years, 54% of the respondents belong to the age group of above 48 years.

OCCUPATION OF THE RESPONDENTS:

The below table shows the type of respondents of the respondents surveyed.

Occupation	No Of Respondents
Student	0
Business	50
Private Employee	32
Govt Employee	18
Total	100

INFERENCE: From the above table 0% of the respondents are students, 50% of the respondents are businessmen, 32% of the respondents are private employee, 18% of the respondents are Govt employee.

FACTORS	NO.OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
EMPLOYEES	15	30%
BUSINESS PERSONNEL	26	52%
PROFESSION	3	6%
STUDENTS	6	12%
TOTAL	50	100%

Table : 1

Graph 1:

Interpretation:

According to my survey, it can be seen from the above table that indicates Employees 15 (30%), Business Personnel 26 (52%), Profession 3 (6%) and Students 6 (12%), are preferring to purchase AIRTEL.

VI. CONCLUSION

According to the project's findings, maintaining the service in accordance with the influence of advertising on consumer purchasing behaviour and raising awareness via word-of-mouth are two effective ways to promote any service.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

COMPANY PROFILE ---www.bharati.com

PRINCIPLES OF MARKETING MANAGEMENT

---- PHILIP KOTLER

MODERN MANAGEMENT---

R.S.N.PILLAI

NEWSPAPERS---- THE HINDU

THE ECONOMIC TIMES